

determined (Table 1). Optimum levels were based on regression lines developed at the site using 6-7 irrigation levels. (In a regression line, a point above optimum was termed supraoptimum; a point below, suboptimum.)

The soil is a sandy loam calcareous (23% CaCO₃) with pH of 8.4 (1:2 soil:water), developed from silty alluvium sediments with EC less than 0.6 dS/m. The water table was 2.0-6.1 m from the surface. Soil sampled from 0-30 cm contained 275 kg N/ha, 21.5 kg P/ha, and 83 kg K/ha.

Variation in irrigation levels and cropping sequences caused significant

differences in yield. The interaction between irrigation and cropping sequence was also significant. At each irrigation level, rice - potato - green gram yielded the most, followed by rice - winter maize - black gram. At the suboptimal and optimal levels, yields did not differ significantly between sequences containing mustard and gram. At the supraoptimal level, gram had a significant decrease in yield compared with mustard because gram does not respond to more frequent irrigation (Table 2).

Variation in net return due to irrigation level and cropping sequence was significant, as was the interaction effect

between irrigation and cropping sequence. Net return grew significantly with each increase in irrigation level for rice - potato - green gram, but for rice - winter maize - black gram, net return increased only up to the optimum irrigation level. Net returns were not significantly different between rice - wheat - green gram and rice - winter maize - black gram at the suboptimal level; at higher levels, net return was superior for the latter (Table 2). ■

Research methodology

An improved protocol for nonradioactive DNA analysis using digoxigenin labeling

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We report here a simplified protocol for detecting membrane-bound DNA based on digoxigenin (DIG) labeling. DIG is a steroid which occurs naturally only in digitalis plants (*Digitaria lunata* and *D. purpurea*). The possibility of contaminating most biological samples with DIG-containing compounds is, therefore, minimal. In this procedure, the DIG-labeled DNA is hybridized to the target DNA. The labeled DNA hybrid is then detected in a two-step procedure, where an anti-DIG antibody conjugated to alkaline phosphatase is bound to the DIG-labeled probe. The physical location of the hybrids is then determined by using chromogenic or luminescent substrates for alkaline phosphatase.

DNA labeling

DIG is purchased as a labeled DNA precursor, DIG-11-dUTP (Boehringer Mannheim). This can be incorporated into a probe DNA by one of three methods: nick translation, random priming, or amplification using the polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Our random priming and PCR labeling procedures are described.

DNA labeling by random priming.

Probe DNA template is denatured for 10 min in a boiling water bath and chilled immediately on ice. The following are then added to every 10 µl of template (100 ng to 3 µg DNA): 2 µl of 10X primer mix (random hexanucleotides, 62.5 U/ml; Tris-HCl, 0.5 M (pH 7.2); MgCl₂, 0.1 M; dithioerythritol, 1 mM; and 2 mg/ml bovine serum albumin), 2 µl 10X dNTP mix (dATP, 1 mM; dCTP, 1 mM; dGTP, 1 mM; dTTP, 0.65 mM; and DIG-11-dUTP, 0.35 mM), 5 µl sterile distilled water, and 1 µl Klenow enzyme (2 U/µl). The resulting mixture is incubated for 2 h to overnight at 37 °C. The reaction is stopped by adding 2 µl of 0.2 M EDTA (pH 8). The labeled probe is precipitated by adding 10 µl of tRNA (2 mg/ml), 3.5 µl of 3 M sodium acetate, and 100 µl of cold absolute ethanol. The addition of tRNA is optional but beneficial if labeling a small amount of DNA. The labeled DNA is pelleted at 12,000 rpm for 5 min, rinsed with 70% ethanol, vacuum-dried, and resuspended in 200 µl TE-SDS (Tris-HCl, pH 8, 10 mM; EDTA, 1 mM; SDS, 0.1 %). A fifth of the reaction is added to every 10-15 ml of hybridization buffer. The rest of the probe keeps indefinitely at 20 °C.

DNA labeling using PCR (adapted from a procedure from the International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center).

A reaction mixture for thermal amplification is made with the following constitution: distilled water, 29.6 µl; 10X Taq incubation buffer (Tris-HCl, pH 8, 100 mM; MgCl₂, 15 mM; KCl, 500 mM; and gelatin, 1 mg/ml), 5 µl; 10X DIG-dNTP mix (dATP, dCTP, and dGTP, 2 mM each; dTTP, 1.65 mM; and DIG-dUTP, 0.35 mM), 5 µl; primer mix (1 µM each of M13-20 = 5'-GTAAAACGACGGCCAGT-3' and M13-R = 5'-AACAGCTATGACCATG-3'), 5 µl; Taq polymerase (5 U/µl), 0.4 µl; and template DNA (1 ng/µl), 5 µl. Thermal cycling is performed using the following program: 94 °C (1 min), 1 cycle; 94 °C (1 min), 55 °C (2 min), and 72 °C (1 min), 25 cycles; and 72 °C (1 min), 1 cycle. The amplified product is precipitated by adding 5 µl of 3 M sodium acetate and 100 µl of chilled absolute ethanol, rinsed with 70% ethanol, vacuum-dried, and resuspended in 50 µl of TE (Tris-HCl, pH 8, 10 mM; and EDTA, 1 mM). Typical yield is 2.5 µg. The M13 primers work for sequences cloned in pUC, pGEM, and pBluescript plasmids.

Hybridization and washing

The choice of blotting membrane is extremely important. We have had best results with positively charged nylon membrane (Hybond N⁺, Amersham). The

membrane is manipulated with utmost care and is only handled at the edges with forceps. The following is our procedure for hybridizing probes to DNA transferred on Hybond-N⁺.

Blots are hybridized at 68 °C overnight in plastic boxes or sealed plastic bags using the following hybridization solution: 5X SSC; dried skim milk, 0.5%; sarcosyl, 0.1 %; SDS, 0.02%; and salmon sperm DNA, 100 µg/ml. Blots are pre-hybridized initially for at least an hour in the solution without the probe. About 2.5 ml of probe-containing hybridization solution is used per 100-cm² blot. Probes are denatured by boiling for 15 min in a water bath prior to addition to the hybridization solution. After hybridization, the following stringency washes are performed: twice for 5 min at room temperature with 2X SSC, 0.1 % SDS; and twice for 15 min at 68 °C with 0.1X SSC, 0.1 % SDS. The prehybridization and probe-containing hybridization solution may be kept at -20 °C and reused several times. The probe should be denatured, however, by boiling the solution in a water bath for 15 min before use.

Detection of hybrids

Chromogenic method. The following incubations for detection of probe-hybrids are performed at room temperature. The blot is washed for 1 min with buffer 1 (Tris-HCl, pH 7.5, 100 mM; and 150 mM NaCl) and incubated in buffer 2 (buffer 1 with 100 µg/ml sheared salmon sperm DNA and 2% dried skim milk or casein, or 0.5% blocking reagent [Boehringer Mannheim]) for 30 min. Buffer 2 is replaced with buffer 1 containing 1.50 mU/ml anti-DIG alkaline phosphatase conjugate (anti-DIG-AP [Boehringer Mannheim]) and the blot is incubated for another 30 min. Unbound anti-DIG-AP is then removed by two rinses of buffer 1 (plus 0.3% Tween 20), each for 15 min. The blot is washed for 2 min in buffer 3 (Tris-HCl, pH 9.5, 100 mM; NaCl, 100 mM; and MgCl₂, 50 mM) and incubated with color substrate. The color substrate is prepared by adding 45 µl NBT (nitroblue tetrazolium salt, 75 mg/ml in 70% dimethylformamide) and 35 µl BCIP

(toluidinium salt of 5-bromo-4-chloro-3-indolyl phosphate, 50 mg/ml in dimethylformamide) to 10 ml of buffer 3. Hybrid signals are visible after 1-2 h. The intensity of the signals is adjusted by shortening or prolonging the incubation of blots in the color substrate, but this is normally less than a day. After maximum strength of signals is reached, the blots are washed twice in distilled water and dried. Buffer 2 can be reused several times if kept frozen during storage. The anti-DIG-AP solution in buffer 1 may also be reused if several blots have to be processed but it is only active within 12 h at 4 °C. Color blots can be reprobbed, although somewhat laboriously, by washing off the stain with dimethylformamide at 65 °C. After decolorization, the probe is stripped off by incubating the blots twice in 0.4 M NaOH for 15 min at 45 °C. Blots are then rinsed with water and washed twice for 5 min with 2X SSC

at room temperature. The blots may be stored dry or used directly for reprobbed.

Luminescent method. This is the method of choice for blots that require frequent reprobbed and is based on the emission of light during the dephosphorylation of AMPPD (3-[2'-spiroadamantane]-4-methoxy-4-[3'-phosphoryloxy]-phenyl-1,2-dioxetane). This procedure is similar to the chromogenic technique except that the substrate solution contains AMPPD instead (100 µg/ml AMPPD in buffer 3). Blots in AMPPD solutions are wrapped neatly in clingfilm. X-ray film is exposed to these blots for 15 min or more (depending on the intensity of signals). Multiple exposures are possible since the light emission persists for 24 h. The AMPPD solution in buffer 3 can be reused up to five times within 2 mo of preparation. Probes are stripped in a manner similar to that in the chromogenic method. ■

Nonradioactive DNA analysis using biotin labeling and chemiluminescent detection

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The most common method for detecting DNA in blots involves using radioactively labeled probes. Technical advances in nonradioactive detection methodologies have made these attractive alternatives. The reagents for nonradioactive DNA analysis are relatively stable (the half-life of the most commonly used radioisotope, ³²P, is 14 d). Using nonradioactive labeling reduces the frequency of shipping perishable and hazardous materials. Using nonradioactive probes eliminates exposure to radioactive materials and disposal of radioactive waste. Additionally, labeled probes are stable for at least several months.

Several types of labeling and detection kits are available commercially. They vary in molecules used for labeling DNA (the ligand) and the labeling and detec-

tion methods. The biotin-avidin system is one of the most widely used nonradioactive labeling methods. Biotin is incorporated into the probe DNA as biotin-11-dUTP. Subsequently, avidin conjugated to alkaline phosphatase is bound to the biotin. The complex is detected using a chemiluminescent substrate for alkaline phosphatase (AMPPD, 3-[2'-spiroadamantane]-4-methoxy-4-[3'-phosphoryloxy]-phenyl-1,2-dioxetane). A simplified protocol based on the biotin-avidin system follows.

DNA labeling and detection

Biotin, purchased as biotin-11-dUTP, is substituted for dTTP in labeling reactions. The biotin can be incorporated into the DNA probe by nick translation, random priming, or amplification using polymerase chain reaction (PCR). Commercially prepared kits are available for each of these methods. The protocols for labeling and detection described here have been used with kits from Tropix (47 Wiggins Ave., Bedford, Massachusetts 01730, USA).

DNA labeling using nick translation. Add the following to a microcentrifuge tube: 10 µl of DNA sample containing 0.03-2 µg DNA, 3 µl of dNTP mixture,